

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

D4.1: Guideline on model's credibility standards

Deliverable information	
WP number and title	WP4 - Technical Standards and Regulatory aspects
Lead beneficiary	DIN
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	30/06/2024
Actual date of delivery	
Author	DIN
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implemented an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by DIN and the work package leader (UNICT - Francesco Pappalardo). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V1.0	29/04/2024	Draft	UNICT	Creation of the document
V2.0	07/06/2024	Draft	DIN	revision
V3.0	08/06/2024	Draft	UNIBO	MV revision
				Final revision
V1_rev1	23/05/2025	Final		Revised version to comply requests by the EC

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction to the regulatory work package

WP4's main target is to lower barrier B3, "No clear regulatory pathways", by pursuing the first qualification of new In Silico Trials methodologies to be used in the regulatory evaluation of new medical products. It also aims to explore new regulatory pathways enabled by In Silico Trials for three main categories of medical products: medicinal products, medical devices, and advanced therapeutic medicinal products (ATMPs). WP4's activities focus mainly on two aspects: on one side, WP4 is trying to understand which technical standard should be used to qualify the credibility of In Silico Trials solutions in Europe and for products other than medical devices. This is done by performing an exploratory activity toward the other standardisation bodies potentially involved (ISO, CEN), as well as toward EMA and at least one notified body. The ultimate goal is to decide if using the ASME VV40.2018 standard in Europe is sufficient or if additional standardisation activities are necessary. Conversely, WP4 members will work on the regulatory qualification of the two Fast Accreditation Track (FAT) applications released from WP2 at M06.

1.2. Description of the content of this deliverable

This deliverable describes the outcomes of the overview of existing standards, the networking activities, and the ongoing standardisation activities.

2. Overview of existing standards

It is crucial for a Research and Innovation (R&I) project to know the state of the art in the areas relevant to or connected to the project. Since standards reflect this state of the art in a specific area, R&I projects need to have an overview of the standardisation landscape related to the project. This knowledge enables the project to tailor its results or findings to current market requirements and helps ensure that they are interoperable with existing solutions. R&I projects need to consider the developments within other relevant activities. Irrespective of the technical merits of the R&I project developments, these efforts will be inconsequential if developed in isolation, and the market decides to follow another path.

Consequently, an overview of the existing European and international standardisation world was first prepared and compiled by DIN. The first research in the databases of the standardisation organisations (in particular CEN and ISO) of DIN showed that few European and international standards exist in the field of *in silico* models. Yet, some standards should be considered for partial aspects (e.g. general risk management, evaluation of software as a medical device) (an example for a search is shown in figure 1). The most important standard is ASME VV 40-2018, “Assessing Credibility of Computational Modelling Through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices”. In the ISO/TC 276 “Biotechnology” research area, the ISO/TS 9491-1 “Biotechnology - Predictive computational models in personalised medicine research - Part 1: Constructing, verifying and validating models” will be relevant. This standard is in the process of being revised to the international standard. Also, the second part of the Technical Specification ISO/TS 9491-2, “Biotechnology - Predictive computational models in personalised medicine research - Part 2: Guidelines for implementing computational models in clinical integrated decision support systems”, is under development. Two committees are relevant for the specific area of “Artificial Intelligence”: CEN/CLC/JTC 21 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42. Under the lead of these committees, several standards and technical reports are being developed to deal with issues of conformity and risk management, e. g., ISO/IEC 23894:2023 “Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance on risk management”. These documents shall also be considered, during the preparation of a standard for *in silico* models.

Example of a result from the DIN database search for 3 selected committees

Figure 1: Example of a search

3. Network activities

Experts from various fields were contacted at conferences and meetings of CEN and ISO technical committees.

In the field of standardisation, contact was established with ISO/TC 276, particularly with WG 5. An official Liaison of ISW (via Avicenna Alliance) with ISO/TC 276/WG 5 “Data processing and integration” is founded. This allows the experts to contribute with comments and ideas to revise the two parts of ISO/TS 9491.

In May 2022 Todd Cooper, convenor of WG 11 “Personalized digital health” and now chair of ISO/TC 215 “Health Informatics”, was informed about the activities of the ISW project. There was interest in the project, but due to the already large work program, the possibilities for managing a project in the field of verification and validation for *in silico* models were considered difficult.

On 6th July 2022, the first exchange with Regina Geierhofer, the chair of IEC/TC 62 “Electrical equipment in medical practice”, took place and a great deal of interest in the project was generated. From the point of view of IEC/TC 62, the project is a good addition to the current work program. The IEC/TC 62 work program, in particular the work of the SNAIG (Software Network and Artificial Intelligence Advisory Group) working group, was presented to interested parties of the ISW project on 21st July 2022.

During the VPH Conference in Porto in September 2022, the co-operation with IEC/TC 62 and the idea of a project on verification and validation for *in silico* models were presented. The next exchange with the IEC group took place in October 2022. At the IEC/TC 62 plenary meeting on 4th November 2022, the ISW project was presented to all IEC/TC 62 members for the first time, and there was general approval for collaboration. In 2023, a possible project lead was found on the IEC/TC 62 side, and the first exchange with her and experts of the ISW project took place in June 2023. The official liaison with the ISW project (via Avicenna Alliance) was formally agreed upon at the end of the year 2023. The proposed new project was also presented to ISO/TC 210, “Quality management and corresponding general aspects for products with a health purpose including medical devices”, on 15th December 2023. ISO/TC 210 currently has no capacity for the project but is interested in principle.

Also, an exchange with the persons responsible for the ASME VV 40-2018 took place, and an official liaison between IEC/TC 62 and the ASME committee was established.

The future standardisation project related to “*Establishing the credibility of computational modelling in the field of medical devices through verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification*” is to be initiated in IEC/TC 62.

4. Ongoing standardisation activities

As a first step, interest in the standardisation project was sought in a suitable technical committee.

Interest was generated in IEC/TC 62 “Electrical equipment in medical practice”, and a working group and project will be established. As ISO/TC 276/WG 5, ISO/TC 215, and ISO/TC 210 are also generally interested in this standard, it is possible that a joint IEC/ISO standard could be published at a later stage. A working group can only be established if the technical committee accepts a work item (in this case, IEC/TC 62) and five countries have expressed their interest in participating in the project.

A project at ISO and IEC goes through the following processing stages:

- Preparatory stage (Working Draft = WD);
- Committee stage (Committee draft = CD);
- Enquiry stage (Draft International Standard = DIS);
- Approval stage (Final Draft International Standard = FDIS);
- Publication stage (International standard).

The Preparatory stage includes the preparation of the new work item proposal. The ASME standards (VV10, VV20 and VV40) provide input for (physics-based) computational modelling and simulation. The ISO/TC 276 standards (ISO/TS 9491-series) provide input for data-driven computational models. IEC/TC62 aligns it with the medical device base standards and the need for market access. It also contributes to machine learning standards for medical AI, which often face the same challenges as data-driven models. Based on these ideas, some ISW experts drafted, in cooperation with the Secretary of IEC/TC 62 and the potential convenor of the new working group, a new work item proposal. This proposal includes:

- the title of the project “*Establishing the credibility of computational modelling in the field of medical devices through verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification*”;
- the scope of the project and
- the background and task of the project.

The request for a new work item and the appointment of experts for this project will be started in June 2024. The standard shall be prepared within the given timeline when the work item is accepted. The Technical Committee decides if the standard will be finalised in 18 (only for standards with high market relevance and urgency, where preliminary work is usually already available), 24 or 36 months. The next step is to prepare a first draft, which will be sent out for comments (committee stage) within IEC/TC 62.

In addition to the above-mentioned ASME VV 40-2018 standard, the guideline “Toward good simulation practice – Best practice for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products” published by the ISW project experts will also be useful for the content of the standard, when preparing the draft in the committee stage.

The DIS document will be prepared depending on the comments received on the CD. If there are no major technical comments in the DIS survey and no country rejects the document, the FDIS stage can be skipped. Usually, however, there are also further comments in the DIS stage, which - as in the CD stage - are evaluated by the WG and the document is adapted accordingly.

5. Concluding remarks

The first step is to establish a new work item and a working group. A first draft is hoped to be finalised during the remaining ISW project period. However, the standardisation project will still require work even after the ISW project has ended (comment evaluations, revision of the draft), but the groundbreaking work has been started through the project.

6. Addendum – a guideline for companies

In the Grant Agreement, in relation to this deliverable, we wrote: “DIN will also lead the compilation of a guideline produced by the ISW consortium to help companies active in this field to choose the best qualification pathway. The guideline will be published on the project web site by M42 (D4.1)”. However, as the project developed, it became evident that while the ISW consortium had been successful in instigating the creation of an IEC/ISO working group, the timeline of this standardisation effort was going to be incompatible with that of the project. So, in June 2024, when this deliverable was due, it was not possible to provide any further guidance to the companies, as the Grant Agreement requested.

Nearly one year after we insert this addendum, upon request of the EC, and made publicly available this deliverable on Zenodo, as originally planned.

Unfortunately, the situation today is not much better than that of June 2024. The IEC/TC 62 “Medical equipment, software, and systems” has established, in February 2024, the Preliminary Work Item PWI “Establishing the credibility of computational modelling in the field of medical devices through verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification”. But since then, there has been little public activity around this standard, as far as we know. The next step in the project, called NWP (new work item proposal), is due by February 2026, though. Then the timeline in the IEC will be started. It is thus impossible to recast a timeline for the completion of this standardisation effort, which is, of course, totally out of the control of the ISW consortium.

To further complicate the situation, the recent activities of the U.S. Department of Government Efficiency (DOGE) target a budget cut of 19% for the FDA, which has caused the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) to terminate 3,500 employees at the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) on April 1, 2025. Among the layoffs, we must mention that of Tina Morrison, former Director of the Office of Regulatory Science and Innovation in the Office of the Chief Scientist at the FDA, and the main champion of in silico methodologies within the FDA.

All these things considered, providing a guideline for companies is not easy. Below we summaries our key suggestions, keeping in mind the extreme volatility of the environment. We will divide our recommendations into three categories: Digital Twins in Healthcare (DTH), Medical Device Development Tools (MDDT), and Drug Development Tools (DDT).

6.1. Digital Twins in Healthcare

DTHs can be used as In Silico Trials technologies (for example, see our [ForceLoss](#) solution, where a DTH is used to stratify patients to be enrolled in trials on sarcopenia treatments). While the ASME VV40:2018 targets MDDTs, FDA has made clear in various documents that the same technical standard can be used to document the credibility of a predictive software as a medical device (the regulatory category for DTHs). Thus, our recommendation to companies is:

- Pursue the CE Marking of your DTH solution as a predictive Medical Device Software according to the Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR); these are typically in class IIa, but for higher risk applications, they might go in class IIb or III.

- To demonstrate the credibility of the predictive component of the medical device software, follow the ASME VV40:2018.
- Motivate the choice of a non-harmonised standard by the lack of it, and by citing the IEC/TC62/PWI, which recognises the ASME VV40 as the starting point of their future standardisation effort.
- With all the uncertainties associated with the FDA functioning, pursue the marketing authorisation for your DTH in the USA market by submitting a premarket submission, such as a 510(k) clearance or a Premarket Approval (PMA), depending on the risk class. Follow the ASME VV40:2018 to document the credibility of your predictor.

6.2. Medical Device Development Tools

In the USA regulatory system, MDDT should be qualified before being used to produce evidence of safety or efficacy to be used for regulatory purposes. The FDA offers a [well-defined pathway](#) for this, where it is recommended that the ASME VV40:2018 be used to demonstrate the credibility of the predictors.

In the EU regulatory system, no formal qualification process exists for MDDT, but the notified bodies expect evidence of appropriateness for such tools as part of the technical dossier for the new medical device. In this context, if the DTH is CE-marked as medical device software for clinical use, or it is qualified as MDDT by the FDA, such evidence is straightforward. If this is not possible, discuss with the notified body what such evidence would look like.

6.3. Drug Development Tools

Both the FDA-CDER and the EU-EMA recommend that all DDTs be qualified before being used to produce regulatory evidence on new drugs. Both recognise the ASME VV40:2018 as a valid standard for the so-called *technical validation*. However, in addition to this, they require, as part of the qualification process, also evidence of *clinical validation*, following a process similar to that used for experimental biomarkers.

But the Qualification Advice the ISW consortium pursued with EMA, fully documented in [this public report](#), made evident that while there is ample room for *in silico* methodologies in all preclinical studies, especially when used as non-animal alternatives to animal experimentation, EMA sees the role of *in silico* methodologies in clinical studies limited to PKPD and QSP statistical models used for dose-response estimation (at most with some PBPK cases). Interested companies can find more details in the public report "[Regulatory barriers to the adoption of in silico trials](#)".

6.4. Conclusions

One year after the first issue of this deliverable, the landscape has not improved significantly, and the recent staff reduction at the FDA may make it even more complex. Companies may find additional useful elements in our deliverable [D4.4 "Final report on the qualification activities"](#), where we propose specific regulatory pathways for some of the In Silico Trials solutions developed in the project.